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ELECTRON SPIN RESONANCE

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1 Introduction

Laboratory experiments have shown that when a beam of neutral particles is directed into an inhomogeneous magnetic field, it splits into discrete particle beams due to the influence of the field. This was first observed in the so-called Stern–Gerlach experiment, in which neutral silver atoms were used. The results obtained from these experiments indicate that atoms possess an intrinsic and quantized magnetic angular momentum, i.e., spin, which determines the deflection direction of an individual atom in a magnetic field. In order for a classically defined mathematical model describing the magnitude of the magnetic moment to correspond to experimentally observed results, the expression must be balanced with a term that defines the relationship between the spin and the orbital magnetic moments of electrons. This empirically determined term is called the g-factor. [1]

The purpose of this laboratory work was to observe the phenomenon of electron spin resonance, as well as the underlying Zeeman effect. In the experiment, the different energy states of electrons in atoms in an external magnetic field were measured by utilizing the energies of emitted/absorbed electromagnetic radiation. Based on the results obtained from the experiment, the aim is to determine the g-factor.

Quantum mechanical experiments can be challenging, as they are highly sensitive to measurement errors. Small differences in the experimental setup can lead to significant differences in results. In this experiment, the greatest challenges and sources of inaccuracy are the precise initial setup of the experimental arrangement and recording the results from the measurement instruments.

The electron g-factor is already a very precisely determined physical constant, so in this laboratory work the main goal is to illustrate the quantum mechanical behavior of atoms and the phenomenon of spin resonance. Spin resonance has many practical applications, for example in medicine in MRI imaging. [2] A better understanding of the quantum mechanical nature of particles as well as qualitative models helps in the development of new applications.

2 Abstract

In this work, electron spin resonance and the Zeeman effect were studied with the aim of illustrating quantum mechanics and determining the electron g-factor experimentally. The measurements were carried out using a DPPH sample in the magnetic field of an electromagnet. The work highlighted the importance of spin resonance in quantum applications.

3 Model and methods

3.1 Particle in a magnetic field

When a neutral atom is introduced into an external magnetic field, a magnetic moment acts on it, arising from the motion of electrons in orbitals and from the spin property of electrons. The total interaction energy between the magnetic moment and the magnetic field is given by:

$$E_M = -\boldsymbol{\mu}\bar{\mathbf{B}} \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ describes the magnetic dipole moment and $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$ the magnetic flux density. The dipole moment can be decomposed into vector components based on the electron's orbital motion and spin:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{spin} + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{orb}. \quad (2)$$

The orbital dipole moment of the electron can be modeled within classical physics as:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{orb} = -\frac{e}{2m}\mathbf{l}, \quad (3)$$

where e is the elementary charge of the electron, m is the mass of the electron, and \mathbf{l} is the electron's orbital angular momentum. The value of the angular momentum depends on which orbital the electron occupies, since the geometric properties of orbitals differ significantly from one another.

On the other hand, the electron's intrinsic spin creates circulating charge distributions that possess a dipole moment in an external magnetic field. For this reason, it can be assumed that the magnetic moment associated with spin follows a relation of the type in Equation 3. Determining this

would, however, require computing a volume integral over the electron charge density, which is impossible. Instead, it can be assumed that the relation in Equation 3 applies to the spin magnetic moment if a correction term is added:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{spin} = -g_e \frac{e}{2m} \mathbf{S} = -g_e \mu_B \frac{\mathbf{S}}{\hbar} \quad (4)$$

Here \mathbf{S} is the electron spin, μ_B is the Bohr magneton, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, and g_e is the g-factor, which contains the information from the volume integral. [1]

3.2 Zeeman effect

In the laboratory experiment, DPPH (Diphenyl-Picryl-Hydrazyl) is chosen as the sample material because it has only one unpaired electron per molecule and its orbital angular momentum moment is zero, i.e., the dipole moment $\boldsymbol{\mu} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{spin}$. Due to these properties, the mathematics used simplifies considerably, since in the mathematical models only a single unpaired electron needs to be considered. Substituting the dipole moment obtained from Equation 4 into Equation 1 gives:

$$E = g_e \mu_B \frac{\mathbf{S}}{\hbar} \cdot \mathbf{B} \quad (5)$$

Into this, one can substitute the magnitude of the electron spin $S = \hbar m_s$, where m_s is the spin quantum number. The possible values of the electron spin quantum number are $-1/2$ or $1/2$, yielding the interaction energy:

$$E = \pm \frac{1}{2} g_e \mu_B B. \quad (6)$$

From this it is seen that in a magnetic field, the binding energy of the molecule's unpaired electron can, depending on the spin quantum number, either increase or decrease linearly as a function of the magnetic flux density of the external magnetic field. This phenomenon is called the Zeeman effect, in which a single energy level splits into two (depending on the system also into more) possible energy levels [3].

In Figure 1, the splitting of energy levels from the ground state is observed. From the graph, the difference between the split energy levels can also be

inferred:

$$\Delta E = g_e \mu_B B. \quad (7)$$

Figure 1: Electron energy level values as a function of magnetic flux density

3.3 Electron spin resonance

In an external magnetic field, the Zeeman effect causes an energy shift in the atom's electron shell that, depending on the electron spin value, is greater or smaller than the ground-state energy. In this state, an electron in the same orbital can transition between the higher and lower energy levels by emitting or absorbing electromagnetic radiation. In connection with a change in energy state, the electron spin quantum number changes to the value corresponding to that state. Based on Figure 1, it is observed that this leads to a change in the spin quantum number: $\Delta m_s = \pm 1$. This phenomenon is called electron spin resonance. [3]

The energy released in a spin-resonance transition corresponds to the energy of electromagnetic radiation:

$$\Delta E = hf \quad (8)$$

where E is the energy of the electromagnetic wave, h is Planck's constant, and f is the frequency of the radiation. Substituting this into Equation 6 yields the relationship between the Zeeman effect and spin resonance:

$$hf = g_e \mu_B B. \quad (9)$$

The dependence given by Equation 9 applies to materials that have only one unpaired electron and whose angular momentum is zero. This property can be utilized in determining the g-factor.

In the laboratory work, the DPPH sample is exposed to electromagnetic radiation in a homogeneous magnetic field. Because it can be very difficult to find a frequency–magnetic-flux-density pair that satisfies the equation, a varying magnetic field can be used, created by driving alternating current through the electromagnet. In the experiment, Helmholtz coils are used as the electromagnet; they produce a fairly homogeneous magnetic field over a small region, and the flux density is given by:

$$B = (4/5)^{3/2} \mu_0 n \frac{I}{r}, \quad (10)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum permeability, n is the number of turns in the coil, I is the current through the coils, and r is the radius of the coils.

When the result of Equation 10 is substituted into Equation 9, the final dependence is obtained:

$$hf = g_e \mu_B (4/5)^{3/2} \mu_0 n \frac{I}{r} \quad (11)$$

With the equipment, one can record the instantaneous current value and the frequency pair that satisfies Equation 11. From these results, the value of the g-factor can be determined.

3.4 Measurement arrangement

In the laboratory experiment, an adjustable power supply driven by a signal generator is used to produce current for the Helmholtz coils. Electromagnetic radiation is produced for the sample using two different probe coils. The frequency sensor of the electromagnetic radiation and the current through the coils are measured with an oscilloscope. Circuit diagram of the experimental setup:

From Figure 2, it is seen that alternating current is generated for the Helmholtz coils using an adjustable power supply and a signal generator. The signal

average current through the coils. The current value must still be multiplied by two, since the coils are connected in parallel.

In Figure 5, the determination of the values using the oscilloscope is illustrated. The alternating current of the coils is shown as a yellow sine wave, and the probe's DC signal and the downward-pointing current peaks are marked in green:

Figure 3: Current readings of the coils and the probe on the oscilloscope.

Measurements were performed at seven different frequency values, for which the corresponding current values were found. Each measurement was initialized using the oscilloscope, and the readings of the frequency meter and the DC meter were recorded. Because the largest sources of uncertainty in the measurement arose from setting the coils to the correct distance and from reading the oscilloscope, the measurement at each frequency was repeated 5 times such that the coil positioning and the oscilloscope initialization were performed again. The distance between the coils was measured with calipers.

The electromagnetic radiation was produced using two different probe coils. The larger probe coil produced frequencies in the range 15–34 MHz and the smaller probe coil in the range 50–106 MHz. The measurements were divided into seven evenly spaced measurements; three with the larger coil and four

with the smaller coil.

The following information about the coils was recorded, as presented in Table 1:

Coil radius (r)	7.2 cm
Distance between coils (l)	7.2 cm
Number of turns (n)	320

Table 1: Coil parameters

4 Results

In the laboratory experiment, measurements were carried out at 7 different frequency values such that the measurement was repeated five times at each frequency. The measurement results were as follows:

Frequency (MHz)	Currents (mA)					Average
	Measurement 1	Measurement 2	Measurement 3	Measurement 4	Measurement 5	
15.59	410.0	406.3	408.3	393.7	400.1	403.68
24.62	541.2	553.7	550.0	549.0	560.0	550.78
34.29	711.0	706.6	711.1	713.3	719.5	712.30
54.36	982.4	980.3	1026.7	974.2	991.6	991.04
69.28	1272.5	1240.9	1267.6	1240.7	1283.9	1261.12
87.69	1581.3	1572.4	1565.6	1571.6	1568.5	1571.88
106.95	1882.0	1920.3	1884.4	1878.3	1872.8	1887.56

Table 2: Measurement results.

Table 2 presents the measured current values as a function of frequency. During each measurement, the frequency was kept constant. The results can be presented graphically:

In Figure 4, spin resonance frequencies are presented as a function of the measured current. From the graph, it can be seen that they have a linear relationship. The measured current values can be converted to magnetic flux density based on Equation 10. All current values must also be divided by two, since in the experimental arrangement the coils were connected in parallel in the circuit.

Table 3 presents the magnetic flux density values inside the Helmholtz coils calculated from the measured current values.

A straight line according to Equation 9 can be fitted to these results, and its slope and the confidence interval of the slope error can be calculated. Based on Equation 9, the slope of the fitted line corresponds to the electron g-factor.

Figure 4: Resonance frequency as a function of current

Calculated magnetic flux densities B (mT)				
Measurement 1	Measurement 2	Measurement 3	Measurement 4	Measurement 5
0.8192	0.8119	0.8159	0.7867	0.7995
1.0814	1.1064	1.0990	1.0970	1.1190
1.4001	1.3975	1.4119	1.4290	1.4253
1.9630	1.9588	2.0515	1.9466	1.9814
2.5409	2.5427	2.4795	2.5325	2.5439
3.1597	3.1419	3.1283	3.1401	3.1361
3.7606	3.8365	3.7654	3.7532	3.7422

Table 3: Magnetic flux density measurement results

Figure 5 presents spin resonance frequencies as a function of magnetic flux density. All possible frequency–magnetic-flux-density pairs lie on the straight line. Using the slope of the line fitted to the data, the value of the electron g-factor can be calculated based on Equation 9:

$$g_e = k \frac{h}{\mu_B}, \quad (12)$$

where g_e is the electron g-factor and k is the slope of the fitted line.

Based on the slope determined from the data, the value of the g-factor and

Figure 5: Spin resonance frequency as a function of magnetic flux density.

its 95% confidence interval are presented in Table 4:

	Value
Electron g -factor	2.20526
95% confidence interval	2.20526 ± 0.00011

Table 4: Computed results for the electron g -factor

The obtained result is reasonable and corresponds fairly well to the value reported in the literature.

4.1 Error estimates and calculations

The implementation of this laboratory work is highly sensitive to gross errors. The most significant sources of error were positioning the coils and the sample at the desired distances from each other. In addition, visually determining results from the oscilloscope was challenging, which exposed the experiment to gross errors. Due to these sources of error, measurements were performed five times for each frequency, such that the positions of the coils and the sample and the current values were re-initialized using the oscilloscope.

On the other hand, multiple measuring devices were used in the work, which increases the risk of systematic error. Incorrect calibration of the instruments or their method of use may have introduced systematic error into the measurements.

The error estimate in this analysis is based on the standard deviation of the residuals of the fitted linear model. The residuals are computed by subtracting the fitted value from the measured value (frequency) for each measurement. The standard deviation of these residuals describes how well the data fits the linear model and provides an estimate of the scatter in the measurement results. Based on this standard deviation, the 95% confidence interval was calculated using Matlab (R2024a) with the command $1.96 * std_err$, which reflects the impact of measurement errors and model uncertainty on the fit. This error estimate was used because it accounts for the scatter of all measurement points and does not make assumptions, for example, about the uniformity of the measurements. This approach enables a more accurate confidence interval calculation, since it is not very sensitive to the influence of individual erroneous measurement results. In addition, the uncertainties of all variables are not known in this work, so this method provides the best computed error estimate.

4.2 Validation of results

The electron g-factor has been determined experimentally with very high precision. At present, the most accurate measured value is $2.0023193043622 \pm 15 * 10^{-13}$ [2]. The obtained result corresponds fairly well to the true value; the result differs by only about 10.1% from the desired result. On the other hand, it is observed that the error bounds of the measured result are very small relative to the result: the computed 95% confidence interval contains only a variation of $\pm 0.005\%$. From this it can be concluded that the variance of the measurement points is quite small, i.e., the coarse error margin of the measurements is very small. The individual measurements have therefore been made to correspond to one another quite well.

Because the true value does not fall within the computed error margin and the calculated measurement error is very small, it can be concluded that a systematic error occurred in the measurements. This most likely resulted

from coil positioning, which led to a systematically incorrect value of the magnetic flux density.

5 Summary

The laboratory work focused on studying electron spin resonance and the Zeeman effect, with the aim of illustrating quantum mechanical principles and experimentally determining the electron g-factor. Electron spin resonance arises when the spin of an unpaired electron in a magnetic field responds to electromagnetic radiation, transitioning between two possible energy levels. Utilizing this phenomenon, the resonance frequencies of electrons in a DPPH sample and the corresponding magnetic flux densities produced by Helmholtz coils were measured. The measurements were carried out at varying frequencies and currents, and the obtained results were modeled based on the mathematical expression of the Zeeman effect.

The measurements showed that the spin resonance frequency and the magnetic flux density have a linear relationship, which confirmed the validity of the theoretical model. Computationally, the electron g-factor was obtained as 2.20526 ± 0.00011 , which is somewhat larger than the precisely known value 2.002319. The deviation may indicate systematic errors in the measurement setup, but the accuracy of individual measurements was good, as indicated by the small error margin. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the laboratory work succeeded in confirming the basic principles of spin resonance and the applicability of quantum mechanical models in practical measurements.

Although the results were generally successful, the limitations of the work and sources of error are noteworthy. Systematic errors, such as imperfect coil positioning or possible deficiencies in instrument calibration, may have affected the final results. Visual reading from the oscilloscope also increased the risk of measurement error. In addition, there may have been weaknesses in the design of the experimental setup that prevented a more accurate determination of the g-factor.

In future work, efforts should focus on reducing sources of error and optimizing the experimental setup. For example, more precise coil calibration and automated collection of measurement data could improve the accuracy.

6 Sources

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